

Fermat's Last Theorem:

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

additional proof(v2)

Therefore $(Z - X)$ must be n -th power.

$$Z - X = R^n$$

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Y must be a multiple of R^n . If not, Y^n cannot be a multiple of $(Z - X)$.

$$Y = RA$$

Therefore the ordered pair (X, Y, Z) must be

$$(Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

R is coprime to A . Because if $\gcd(R, A) = g \geq 2$,

$$(Z - R^n)^n + R^n A^n = Z^n$$

Z^n on both sides are canceled and $R^n A^n$ is a multiple of g^{2n} .

all terms except $-\binom{n}{1}Z^{n-1}R^n$ is a multiple of g^{2n} .

So this is contradiction. Therefore $\gcd(R, A) = 1$

Since $Z - X = R^n$, we can let

$$X = xR^n - c$$

$$Z = zR^n - c$$

c is a natural number that satisfy $c < R^n$.

$$X = xR^n - c$$

$$Z = zR^n - c$$

$$Y^n = Z^n - X^n$$

$$= \{(zR^n)^n - \binom{n}{1} (zR^n)^{n-1}c + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} zR^n c^{n-1} - c^n\}$$

$$- \{(xR^n)^n - \binom{n}{1} (xR^n)^{n-1}c + \dots + \binom{n}{n-1} xR^n c^{n-1} - c^n\}$$

$-c^n + c^n$ are canceled and group like terms for c .

Then all terms are multiple of $R^n(z - x)$.

$$Y^n = R^n(z - x) \times (\text{natural number})$$

Since $Y^n = R^n A^n$,

$$A^n = (z - x) \times (f(z, x)) - (\varphi 1)$$

c, n are fixed constant and z, x are variables.

$f(z, x)$ is a natural number.

Thus A^n has $(z - x)$ as a factor.

However,

$$Y^n = R^n A^n = Z^n - X^n = (Z - X) \times \Phi_n(Z, X)$$

Since $(Z - X) = R^n$,

$$A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X) = Z^{n-1} + Z^{n-2}X + \dots + ZX^{n-2} + X^{n-1}$$

Substitute $Z = zR^n + c$, $X = xR^n + c$

$$A^n = \Phi_n(Z, X) = \Phi_n(zR^n + c, xR^n + c) = g(z, x)$$

Since

$$(z - x)f(z, x) = A^n = g(z, x)$$

$$(z - x)f(z, x) = g(z, x)$$

thus $g(z, x)$ has $(z - x)$ as a factor.

Therefore if we substitute $z = x$ into the $g(z, x)$, the value of $g(z, x)$ is 0.

$$\begin{aligned} g(x, x) &= \Phi_n(xR^n + c, xR^n + c) = \Phi_n(X, X) \\ &= \{X^{n-1} + X^{n-1} + \dots + X^{n-1} + X^{n-1}\} \end{aligned}$$

Since the number of the terms in $\Phi_n(Z, X)$ is n ,

$$\begin{aligned} g(x, x) &= \Phi_n(xR^n + c, xR^n + c) = \Phi_n(X, X) = nX^{n-1} \\ &= n(xR^n - c)^{n-1} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore (xR^n - c) = 0$$

$$c = xR^n$$

It is contradiction.

We assumed that $c < R^n$.

But we get

$$c = xR^n$$

for natural numbers c, x, R^n

It is contradiction.

Therefore the ordered pair $(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$ is impossible.